

EDITION OF ONE (EO1) – LITERARY AGENCY

Image – “Seeing and Hearing Things Again”, CEPT University, Ahmedabad, India, April 12, 2017. Photo: Harsh Bhavsar.

0. ABSTRACT

The myth of works is something altogether different than the myth of genius or the myths that objective-empirical scholarship loves to demolish. The auto-hagiographic nature of life-works is effectively “non-human”. The mythos is the mysterium, and vice versa – e.g., in the precise sense that, for Hegel, the ideal is the real and the real is the ideal. It is also possible to say that the ideal *was* the real and that the real *was* the ideal, given that Hegel’s radical and totalizing project toward a system ended up mired in socio-cultural terms once it began to privilege the real and forms of mediation that bordered on an ideological putsch masquerading as pragmatism and a political utilitarianism that could be coopted by the Left or the Right. Marx was, thus, correct to invert and subvert Hegel’s system, insofar as the diachronic political agenda was veering off into dangerous territory. The EO1 agenda, through its elective abolition of intellectual property rights, is, thus, meant as antidote to the travesties of the debauched neoliberal-capitalist Knowledge Commons.

I. INTRODUCTION

Much as E.F. Schumacher predicted in 1973, with the publication of *Small is Beautiful: A Study of Economics as If People Mattered*, the general status for subjects caught in the positivist edicts of the neoliberal-capitalist edufactory is a sense of inhabiting an “abyss of nothingness.” “And what do we get from it today? A view of the world, as a wasteland in which there is no meaning or purpose, in which man’s consciousness is an unfortunate cosmic accident, in which anguish and despair are the only realities. If by means of a real education man manages to climb to what Ortega calls ‘the Heights of Our Times’ or ‘the Height of the Ideas of our Times,’ he finds himself in an abyss of nothingness.”¹

¹ E.F. Schumacher, “The Greatest Resource – Education”, pp. 83-107, in E.F. Schumacher, *Small is Beautiful: A Study of Economics as If People Mattered* (New York: Harper Perennial, 2010), p. 96; first published *Small is Beautiful: A Study of Economics as If People Mattered* (London: Blond & Briggs, Ltd., 1973).

Thus, Schumacher suggested (echoing Freire) that we restore some lost precepts: “Even in the humanities we may get bogged down in a mass of specialised scholarship, furnishing our minds with lots of small ideas just as unsuitable as the ideas which we pick up from the natural sciences. But we may also be more fortunate (if fortunate it is) and find a teacher who will ‘clear our minds,’ clarify the ideas – the ‘large’ and universal ideas already existent in our minds – and thus make the world intelligible for us.”²

II. EO1 PRÉCIS

1. Engage in Collective Production: Authors and cultural producers are encouraged to collaborate on collectively produced works to circumvent traditional notions of authorial privilege and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), thus challenging the capitalist structures that commodify cultural production. 2. Eschew Traditional IPR: Moving away from traditional intellectual property rights frameworks to free cultural works from the constraints of capitalist exploitation. 3. Disrupt the Disruptors: Cultural producers find innovative ways to challenge and disrupt the current cultural and economic systems that privilege certain voices and narratives over others, including questioning the influence of celebrity intellectuals. 4. Explore Alternative Economic Models: Investigate and advocate for economic models that prioritize communal and collective benefits over individual gains, potentially through the radical rethinking of IPR. 5. Promote Absolute Resistance: Embrace strategies that resist the prevailing capitalist narratives and practices, drawing inspiration from historical figures such as Tolstoy and Gandhi, who advocated for radical social change.

Grant funds will be sought and utilized to establish the architecture and working protocols of a borderless, collectivist-based literary agency for works of literary-artistic scholarship produced and editioned under the “No Rights” status defined through the Edition of One (EO1) model. Satellite-based projects within the greater EO1 project will concern the development of a new research and publications ecosystem for nonproprietary works of collectively produced literary-artistic scholarship. Primary costs associated with the global, borderless model will be honoraria for artist-scholars engaged in the project, research sojourns, public events (salons and workshops) to promote the project, and the editioning and dissemination of prototype works.

III. SUMMARY

The EO1 project follows a research PhD in Philosophy, conducted at the Postgraduate School, ZRC SAZU, Ljubljana, Slovenia (2021-2024), concerning forms of research and scholarship that go beyond current academic and art-world conventions and one step beyond Open Access protocols into an as-yet-to-be-defined realm denoted the wild blue yonder. However, the backstory for the PhD includes a five-year experiment in collectively produced performance- and time-based works (transmedia) via the Out of India-Metropolitan Transmedia Authority (OOI-MTA) collective, founded in India in 2017, plus an earlier research PhD, in Architecture, conducted at Deakin University, Geelong, VIC, Australia (2011-2014), and focusing on visual agency in Art and Architecture. The EO1 project is thus yet another exercise in re-collectivizing the nominally solitary and bespoke nature of PhD projects by widening the scope and intentions and returning it all to the greater cultural commons. Key questions to be addressed include how authors and artists (denoted artist-scholars in the ZRC SAZU PhD project) may evade dictates associated with the hyper-commodification of the knowledge commons and “return” works to a non-proprietary status through the elective abolition of IPR. This somewhat troublesome and spectral issue, for artist-scholars, actually first appeared in studies of the archive of French polymath Chris Marker, in the Deakin PhD noted above. It continued to “return” in various forms in postdoctoral research projects in the intervening years only to finally define itself properly in the ZRC SAZU PhD.

The architecture of the borderless literary agency for artist-scholars will be built through a series of research and publication projects and public colloquia. This “architecture” will include establishing a Distributed Autonomous Organization (DAO) on a project-by-project basis, utilizing blockchain and cryptocurrency. The creation of NFTs at the conclusion of a project would be utilized to help fund subsequent projects.

The EO1 project will be multi-nodal. In keeping with the extra-academic, public-facing intentions of the project, salons and soirées would be the preferred event-based means of publicizing the EO1 project, plus de facto

² Ibid. Schumacher opens *Small is Beautiful* with an epigraph that remains true to this day: “A reasonable estimate of economic organisation must allow for the fact that, unless industry is to be paralysed by recurrent revolts on the part of outraged human nature, it must satisfy criteria which are not purely economic.” R.H. Tawney, *Religion and the Rise of Capitalism* (1926), in *ibid.*, p. vii.

methodology for finding fellow-travelers to join in the satellite, project-based operations. These “colloquia” would be developed in association with regional research projects, and be utilized for the presentation of the ongoing, aleatory research protocols.

IV. EO1 DRAFT PROTOCOLS

The following set of protocols for a multi-nodal, borderless collective for the production and dissemination of works of literary-artistic scholarship is intended to counter the current hyper-commodification of both the art-world and academia.

WE ARE YOU

YOU

YOU wish to publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA, venturing into the wild blue yonder of “No Rights”

YOU have no interest in furthering the metrics-driven, academic culture industry and prefer to produce and disseminate your work without concern for mere careerist and/or institutional agendas

YOU prefer to let works speak for themselves and are willing to let works decide where they wish to go and how they are editioned

YOU are willing to transfer your moral rights as author to works

YOU no longer have or never have had any interest in the neoliberal capitalist term *Human Capital* and refuse to leverage your works as private property and/or as commodity

YOU agree that the Republic of Letters (Diderot) and General Intellect (Marx) are hardly the same thing as the neoliberal-capitalist Knowledge Commons

WE

WE are a not-for-profit literary agency established solely for the purpose of assisting authors and artists (and artist-scholars) to produce and disseminate works without any intention of servicing Capital and/or the protocols of the art-academic industrial complex

WE agree that the Republic of Letters (Diderot) and General Intellect (Marx) are hardly the same thing as the neoliberal-capitalist Knowledge Commons

WE wish to help authors and artists (and artist-scholars) publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA, venturing into the wild blue yonder of “No Rights”

WE are not an editorial bureau and do not offer editorial services in any conventional sense

WE, as literary agency, wish to promote iterative, aleatory, and collectivist-based works of literary-artistic scholarship

WE will, without reimbursement, assist authors and artists (and artist-scholars) who wish to publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA in logistics for the production and dissemination of works

WE advocate the elective abolition of intellectual property rights